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Table of Contents

Standardisation of the solution	4
1. Introduction.....	4
2. Validation of simulation methodology.....	5
3. Standardization of the business model solution	8
4. Appendix	18
4.1 Annex 1. Simulation software background information	18

List of Figures

Figure 1: Climate zones map in Europe.....	9
Figure 2: % Correlation (temperature, radiation, global) between 6 general case study cities and Paris.....	9
Figure 3: Screenshot of the Simulation Software	19
Figure 4: Screenshot of the General Results interface	20

List of Tables

Table 1: Simulated and monitored final results in the 3 pilots of CHESS SETUP.....	6
Table 2: Reference prices.....	10
Table 3: Summary Sheet 100% Thermal Demand.. ..	12
Table 4: Summary Sheet 50% Thermal Demand.	13
Table 5: Summary of Reference Cases Results.	15

Standardisation of the solution

1. Introduction

Following the previous deliverable (6.1 - Business models for case studies) which explains how CHESS SETUP solution has been implemented in the three pilots (Lavola, Sant Cugat and Corby), this deliverable describes **how the solution has been standardised to identify additional case studies that might have a viable business case**. These case studies allows to have a general idea of how the system can be replicated in future projects and feeds deliverable 6.4- Market research and exploitation plan.

This deliverable is structured according to the guidelines of the **Grant Agreement**, including two different sections:

- Firstly, under the *Calibration¹ of simulation methodology* section we include the comparison of the empirical results of the pilot cases with the initial expected ones, in order to validate the economic feasibility of the pilot systems. The methodology used to calibrate the simulated results based on real data is also explained. The main objective of the process is that the simulation software results could be a support for decision-making.
- Secondly, under the *Standardization of the business solution* section we describe the elements that have been analysed and standardized through the simulation software to identify additional case studies and provide detailed economic and energy information.

Please note that this deliverable refers to information already included in previous deliverables.

¹ There was a misuse in the definition of the word calibration for this task, being the objective the validation of the simulation software.

Validation is the overall process of testing and comparing the model to see if its behaviour represents a viable and useful alternative means to the real system. This process enables *calibrating the model*, that is, the iterative process of adjusting model parameters until the resulting output data agree closely with the observed system data.

2. Validation of simulation methodology

This section describes how the business models of the three pilot sites have been validated through the results obtained in the simulation software, to provide a realistic approach of the CHESSE SETUP solution performance, **comparing the expected or simulated outcome with the real one.**

The simulation software provides a forecast of the **energy consumptions and savings** (solar production, electrical consumption of the heat pump, gas consumption, and thermal losses among other parameters) as well as an **estimated economic analysis** (investment, economic saving and pay-back) of the solution operation.

The detailed methodology supporting how the simulation tool is capable of providing this economic analysis has been included in the Appendix as Annex. 1 -Simulation software background information.

The simulation software developed in D3.1 has been *verified* and *calibrated* with the results obtained from the energy modelling carried out using Trnsys 18 and Excel-based spreadsheet. Both energy models mentioned above were also used to understand the behaviour of the CHESSE SETUP system in different types of buildings and climate conditions. For further reference on the mentioned models you can consult the deliverables D3.3 System configuration report, D3.7 Pilot's experience report and D5.1 Construction plan report.

The *validation* of the simulation software developed for the 'Deliverable 3.1 Simulation software' was carried out based on a comparative analysis. An analysis and comparison between monitored data from the three pilots and the output data obtained by the simulation conducted with the software for the pilots was done. The values analysed and compared to carry out the validation were the energy results, the CO₂ emissions avoided, and economic savings from operation and maintenance of the system.

The following Table 1 summarizes for each pilot site (Lavola, Sant Cugat and Corby) the CHESSE SETUP simulated performance results versus the real ones. Please note that the performance outcome values have been grouped under the following **five categories** to facilitate its revision:

DEMAND

CONFIGURATION

OPERATION

SAVINGS

ECONOMICS

D6.2 Standardization of business model tool

		Lavola 100% HP ²		Sant Cugat		Corby ³		
		Simulated	Monitored	Simulated	Monitored	Simulated	Monitored	
Demands	Heating and DHW Cons. (kWh/year)	66.504	67.142	1.731.058	2.398.393	6.188	6.300	
	Cooling (kWh/year)	38.271	19.972	-	-	-	-	
	Other electric cons. (kWh/year)	71.995	51.197	1.045.906	1.062.222	3.412	3.013	
Configuration	Total sqm (m ²)	827	827	826	826	167.1	167.1	
	Solar Panels surface (m ²)	56	56	264	264	32	32	
	Solar Panels Peak power (kW)	9,66	9,66	41,60	41,60	5,00	5,00	
	STES Vol (m ³)	33	33	100	100	140	140	
	HP Cons. (kWh/year)	15.211	33.424	31.954	25.944	1.800	2.4400	
	EER	5,00	2,46	5,50	4,86	3,00	2,60	
Operation	PV-T / PV production	Electrical (kWh/year)	14.608	11.058	60.376	41.604	4.269	4.553
		Thermal (kWh/year)	-	-	178.955	-	4.229	4.743
	STES temp.	Min (°C)	27	22	20	11,9	2	20,1
		Max (°C)	32	26	45	42,5	17	22,4
		Average (°C)	29	-	26	19,7	9	-
	Buffer temp.(°C)	27	-	45	43,9	55	55	
	Backup cons. (kWh/year)	0	0	1.532.526	2.174.348	0	0	
Savings	Natural Gas	(kWh _{pci} /year)	63.337	79.364	198.532	224.045	6.876	7.000
		(%)	100%	100%	12,1%	9,3%	100%	100%
	Electricity	(kWh _e /year)	-603	-13.930	28.123	15.660	-2.045	-2.440
		(%)	-0,8%	-23,4%	2,7%	1,8%	-59,9%	-56,9%
	Total energy	(kWh/year)	62.734	65.434	226.655	239.705	4.876	4.560
		(%)	46,4%	47,1%	8,2%	8,3%	47,2%	45,6%
CO ₂	(kgCO ₂ /yr)	16.580	17.671	65.651	57.810	1.841	1.354	
	(%)	62,0%	61%	12,1%	9,2%	85,8%	67,7%	
Economics ⁴	Energy Costs savings	(€/year)	3.986	3.679	17.328	14.417	835	753
		(%)	24,3%	33,4%	8,8%	10,5%	77,0%	77,3%
	Installation Costs (€)	77.000	113.426	604.758	661.922	29.400	22.051	
	Payback (years)	19,5	41,0	36,6	46,5	35,2	29,3	

Table 1: Simulated and monitored final results in the 3 pilots of CHESSE SETUP

For clarification purposes we would like to highlight that the results included in Table 1 are detailed in previous deliverables: The pilots simulated and forecasted results are included in deliverables 'D3.7 Pilot's experience report', 'D5.1 Construction Plan Report' and the empiric or real results are presented in deliverables 'D5.4 Monitoring Results Report' and 'D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies'.

It should also be noted that there are small differences in configuration between the simulated models and the respective pilots implemented. Firstly, the results obtained

²In the simulated scenario it is supposed that, in the algorithm of energy price comparison (gas vs electricity), the use of the heat pump over the gas boiler for heating will be prioritized, even without production of solar energy. In the monitored version: After introducing the CHESSE 3.0 version (described in D. 5.1) and conducting a more detailed analysis of the system operation, it was considered appropriate to meet the heating and cooling demands with a reversible heat pump, rather than using the boiler and the chillers plant.

³Based on the monitored figures, the annual system performance has been forecasted taking into account: site location, solar irradiation, energy bills and expected system performance under standard climatological conditions.

⁴The figures come from 'D3.7' and 'D6.1'. For the 'Installation costs' the total material execution budget was considered.

D6.2 Standardization of business model tool

in the simulations differ from the results obtained from the monitoring periods, mainly due to the lack of reliable data for the one year period analysed. These issues encountered with the data access, are mainly due to the delays in the pilot implementation tasks and the COVID-19 lockdown.

Secondly, and with regards to the results obtained and the difference in the payback periods, it should also be noted that the STES were not "pre-charged" during the summer period, before commissioning and start-up of the pilots. In addition, the occupation and use of the buildings have been different from those defined in the simulations due to the lockdown period.

3. Standardization of the business model solution

This section describes how the empirical results described above, including economic viability of the pilot business models, have been extrapolated to other possible conditions such as different locations, energy resources or technical configurations, to **detect those scenarios (different to the pilot case studies) where there might be a viable business case.**

Standardization elements

First of all, we describe the different business model characteristics or conditions that have been analyzed for the standardization of the CHESSE SETUP solution.

To facilitate the review analysis and justify their importance we have classified all conditions in five different standardization elements:

**CLIMATE
CONDITIONS**

LOCATIONS

**ENERGY
COSTS**

**BUILDING
TYPOLOGIES**

**TECHNICAL
CONFIGURATIONS**

Climate conditions

The three pilot sites – Lavola and Sant Cugat in Spain and Corby in UK - are represented by the coastal Mediterranean climate and the oceanic climate; therefore we have estimated the results of a similar system operating in four additional climate areas in Europe:

- Continental Mediterranean climate, represented by Madrid
- Mountain climate, represented by Davos
- Continental oceanic climate, represented by Berlin
- Continental climate, represented by Stockholm

D6.2 Standardization of business model tool

Figure 1: Climate zones map in Europe. Source: D3.2 Reference cases report.

Figure 2: % Correlation (temperature, radiation, global) between 6 general case study cities and Paris. Source: D3.2 Reference cases report.

Locations

Following the climate conditions described above, the following locations (different to the pilot sites) have been considered:

- Madrid (Spain)
- Berlin (Germany)
- Stockholm (Sweden)
- Davos (Switzerland)

Energy costs

The energy costs for the selected locations has also been considered, taking into account both the electricity and natural gas prices in case of households and non-households buildings. The following Table 2 summarizes the prices considered:

City	Electricity price (€ / kWh)		Natural gas price (€ / kWh)	
	Households	Non-households	Households	Non-households
Madrid	0,219	0,111	0,068	0,028
Berlin	0,297	0,151	0,066	0,034
Stockholm	0,189	0,062	0,113	0,037
Davos	0,203	0.160	0,079	0,033

Table 2: Reference prices. Source: prix-electricite.

Building typologies

The following building typologies have been selected taking into account that although CHESSETUP solution is suitable for many types of buildings, is especially useful for those that have a high hot water demand, as it is nearly constant during the whole year, in contrast to heating demand with greater fluctuations from summer to winter:

- Sports centre
- Hospital
- Hotel (four stars)
- Retirement home
- Multi-family housing
- Single-family housing

Thermal conditions and technical configurations

The following two scenarios have been considered, in order to identify the impact of reductions required, especially to the seasonal storage system:

- Where CHESSE SETUP system covers **100% of the thermal demand**.
- Where the system covers **only 50% of thermal demand**.

Reference cases

In order to determine the feasibility of CHESSE SETUP solution in future projects, the simulation software has been used with the above characteristics or elements providing reference cases. All reference cases simulations are included in D3.2- Reference Cases Report.

Similarly, in D3.2 the study on 'General cases' has been developed, where the performances of six different building typologies in six different cities (climatic zones) have been compared. Temperature and solar radiation are the main factors that affect energy demand and system performance. The following Table 3 summarizes for each type of building in cases of coverage of 100% thermal demand or 50% thermal demand, the relationships between: the surface of solar collection, the volume of the seasonal thermal storage tank, and the surface of the building.

This information can be used as a reference or guide, as they present a first approximation between the main building characteristics (typology, surface availability, size, and location) and the ability to satisfy their thermal demand using the CHESSE SETUP system.

First, we summarize in the following Table 3 the results considering that CHESSE SETUP system covers **100% of the thermal demand**.

100% THERMAL DEMAND

SUMMARY SHEET

m² SOLAR PANEL SURFACE (x100m² building)

		CLIMATE					
		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
BUILDING TYPE	Sports centre	33,3	35,8	96,7	182,2	105,6	124,4
	Hospital	17,5	22,5	61,3	126,3	68,8	83,8
	Hotel 4*	14,5	18,3	50,0	105,0	57,5	70,0
	Retirement home	14,1	18,1	46,6	108,6	56,9	70,7
	Multy-family housing	4,1	5,3	13,8	28,8	15,6	19,4
	Single-family housing	3,3	4,0	11,0	22,0	12,0	14,7

m³ SEASONAL STORAGE TANK VOLUME (x100m² building)

		CLIMATE					
		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
BUILDING TYPE	Sports centre	62,2	93,3	173,3	217,8	217,8	277,8
	Hospital	56,3	80,0	127,5	188,8	161,3	210,0
	Hotel 4*	50,0	75,0	112,5	155,0	147,5	177,5
	Retirement home	51,7	72,4	117,2	156,9	143,1	189,7
	Multy-family housing	13,8	20,0	30,0	41,3	37,5	47,5
	Single-family housing	9,3	14,7	23,3	30,7	29,3	36,7

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

		CLIMATE					
		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
BUILDING TYPE	Sports centre	1,9	2,6	1,8	1,2	2,1	2,2
	Hospital	3,2	3,6	2,1	1,5	2,3	2,5
	Hotel 4*	3,4	4,1	2,3	1,5	2,6	2,5
	Retirement home	3,7	4,0	2,5	1,4	2,5	2,7
	Multy-family housing	3,3	3,8	2,2	1,4	2,4	2,5
	Single-family housing	2,8	3,7	2,1	1,4	2,4	2,5

Table 3: Summary Sheet 100% Thermal Demand. Source: D3.2 Reference cases report.

We have also considered the same analysis but considering the system covers only 50% of thermal demand (Table 4).

50% THERMAL DEMAND SUMMARY SHEET

m² SOLAR PANEL SURFACE (x100m² building)

	CLIMATE						Red
	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm	
Sports centre	10,0	11,1	26,7	44,4	28,9	35,6	72%
Hospital	7,5	10,0	25,0	45,0	28,8	36,3	59%
Hotel 4*	6,5	7,8	20,0	37,5	25,0	30,0	58%
Retirement home	6,5	8,6	21,6	37,9	24,1	31,0	57%
Multy-family housing	1,9	2,1	6,9	10,6	6,9	8,8	56%
Red	58%	59%	59%	66%	60%	59%	

m³ SEASONAL STORAGE TANK VOLUME (x100m² building)

	CLIMATE						Red
	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm	
Sports centre	1,1	4,4	40,0	17,8	71,1	106,7	82%
Hospital	8,8	15,0	27,5	12,5	43,8	62,5	80%
Hotel 4*	7,0	14,5	25,0	17,5	37,5	55,0	79%
Retirement home	10,3	20,7	29,3	17,2	39,7	62,1	76%
Multy-family housing	2,3	4,0	9,4	3,5	10,3	15,0	77%
Red	86%	82%	75%	91%	72%	67%	

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

	CLIMATE						Red
	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm	
Sports centre	0,1	0,4	1,5	0,4	2,5	3,0	35%
Hospital	1,2	1,5	1,1	0,3	1,5	1,7	53%
Hotel 4*	1,1	1,9	1,3	0,5	1,5	1,8	51%
Retirement home	1,6	2,4	1,4	0,5	1,6	2,0	45%
Multy-family housing	1,2	1,9	1,4	0,3	1,5	1,7	50%
Red	69%	58%	38%	72%	26%	16%	

Table 4: Summary Sheet 50% Thermal Demand. Source: D3.2 Reference cases report.

As shown in Table 4, the scenario where CHESSE SETUP system covers only 50 % of thermal demand, the reductions in solar panel surface are about 50 %-60 % while those related to the water tank volume are about 70 %-80 %. We consider the specific case of the Sports Centre relevant, with similar HWS and heating demand which implies that CHESSE SETUP system is covering mainly the HWS demand which is almost constant during the whole year, reducing the demand seasonality and the required water tank volumes.

Real case studies

In addition to the previous analysis of references cases, the implementation of the CHESSE SETUP system has also been simulated in **real case studies** (different to the pilot sites), in which some of the partners have been involved and are potential sites where CHESSE SETUP can be implemented. These sites are the following:

1. A superblock located in Barcelona city (Poblenou Superblock)

2. A residential block located in Barcelona city (Barcelona's Eixample Block)

3. A Hospital in Vilafranca del Penedès, a peri-urban village in Catalunya (Alt Penedès Hospital)

4. A new ecological neighbourhood of 500 dwellings located in Villeneuve-Tolosane (ZAC Les Forses)

For each case, the system has been evaluated (solar surface, storage capacity, and heat pump power) in order to optimize energy performance, technical viability and economic feasibility. All the details are included in D3.2 Reference Cases Report.

For the purpose of this deliverable, the next Table 5 summarizes the main results of the four real case studies, comparing them also to the values of the three pilot cases, having used the simulation software:

Case	Demand (kWh/year)	Solar surface (m ²)	Tank volume (m ³)	Thermal self-sufficiency (%)	Heat pump power (kw)	Investment (€)	Saving (€/year)	Payback
Detail of the 4 simulation scenarios								
1. Poblenou superblock	60.475.206	20.000	50.000	59,3%	5.000	9.645.559	1.031.267	9
2. Barcelona's Eixample block	6.527.001	2.700	8.000	69,8%	800	2.714.373	205.808	14
3. Alt penedès hospital	4.200.000	2.000	6.000	51,2%	600	2.135.849	145.915	14
4. Ecoquartier ZAC Les Forses	2.693.372	3.400	7.600	84,1%	400	2.387.443	68.982	>20

Table 5: Summary of Reference Cases Results. Source: D3.2 Reference cases report.

Conclusions

The most relevant conclusions that can be extracted from the reference cases, the real case studies analysis and its comparison with the pilot cases are:

- CHESSE SETUP solution can be **replicated** and **escalated** for different types of building typologies, climate conditions and energy demands, but is expected to be more profitable in buildings:
 - With **medium-high** and **constant thermal demand**: hotels, hospitals, laundries, sports centre.
 - With available and **easy-access space** to install thermal energy storage, inside or outside the building.
 - **New buildings projects**, as the system will be integrated from the initial design phase of the project.

Furthermore, although the delays in the pilot tasks together with the COVID-19 lockdown and the problems with the data access have made it difficult to analyse the system behaviour and the pilots' results (which varies from the simulations) the pilots' experience have been positive to analyse CHESSE SETUP performance.

In this sense, the following additional conclusions and lessons learned have also been identified from the standardization analysis:

- With regards to the **climate conditions**, CHESSE SETUP can be very suitable for tropical areas, where solar radiation and temperature is very stable during the whole year. This can be applicable in buildings with hot water demand (sports centres, hospitals...) or in areas located in high altitude.

In temperate climates such as in Barcelona, it is possible to build houses with very low or no heating demand by using passive energy efficiency strategies (building insulation, double glazing windows...). In these cases, the system could be sized to supply the only DHW, with very small storage tanks becoming much more profitable.

Buildings located in colder locations with lower solar radiation will require larger solar thermal panel surfaces and seasonal storage tanks, as the energy demand is higher and the energy production for each solar panel is lower.

- With regards to the **investment costs** of the three main elements of the system (solar panels, storage system and heat pump), the seasonal storage system implies more than half of the total investment system costs, so it's important to reduce tank size. Therefore, buildings with high DHW demand require lower tank size and therefore lower economic paybacks are obtained. One possibility is to size the CHESSE SETUP for supplying only DHW demand and a small part of the heating demand. For example, in a multifamily house located in Barcelona,

D6.2 Standardization of business model tool

tank size can be reduced by 4 times and the economic payback by 30% if the system is sized to supply 50% of the heating demand, instead of 100% of it.

It should also be noted that in most cases the main limiting factor to achieve thermal self-sufficiency is the roof surface availability to install solar panels.

- In relation to the **economic payback**, the relation between tank size and solar surface (or supplied demand) is a key factor and will influence the economic payback. It should be reduced as much as possible.

In **existing buildings**, CHESSE SETUP system requires big investment costs but has high economic paybacks. In the case of **new buildings**, lower economic paybacks are obtained. On one hand, because the civil work and system implementation are easier and lower investment costs are required. On the other hand, because the investment and maintenance of the conventional heating system are considered.

One of the **external factors** affecting economic payback is the electricity and natural gas price. In countries with high natural gas prices and low electricity prices, like Sweden, the economic payback is much lower, as with CHESSE SETUP we are saving natural gas, but also the heat pump is consuming electricity. On the opposite side, we place Germany, with low natural gas prices and high electricity prices, obtaining very large economic paybacks. Therefore, the economic payback is very large in Eco-quartier ZAC Les Forses (France) and Low carbon homes in Corby (UK) due to really low gas prices in those countries.

- The **integration of CHESSE SETUP with other energy sources** as biomass, heat waste or geothermal energy can contribute to achieving NZEB for any weather and building typology. Also, the integration with other technologies as hybrid solar panels can contribute to producing both heating and electricity, consumed in the building as it was studied and presented in D3.6 Integration with other energy sources.

4. Appendix

4.1 Annex 1. Simulation software background information

The simulation tool includes libraries with **technical parameters** of the main system components (solar panels, heat pumps, storage systems, pipes...) and some reference values for the system operation (thermal demand distribution by building type, economic data, energy costs...). These libraries have been updated during the development of CHESSE SETUP project adjusting the parameters to the real operation data from the three pilots.

Although the simulation software detail is included in D3.1- Simulation Software and can be found in the CHESSE SETUP web page together with the user guide, we hereafter include additional justification and clarification on how the tool provides the **economic analysis**. We consider this information relevant to this deliverable as one of its objectives has been to identify scenarios which might have a viable business case.

It must be noted that for the economic balance estimation, the system has compared the CHESSE SETUP solution with a conventional heating system based on natural gas boilers.

Once the input data has been filled to the simulation software, the calculation returns the results of the system that has been pre-dimensioned, divided into the following 6 categories:

- General Results
- Solar Panel
- Heat Pump
- Auxiliary System
- Seasonal Storage System
- Losses

Figure 3 below shows the screenshot of the simulation software where this information is detailed:

Figure 3: Screenshot of the simulation software results interface. Source: CHESS SETUP simulation software.

D6.2 Standardization of business model tool

In the screenshot shown in Figure 3, under the category "General Results", we find the following economic results (marked within the red box):

- Invest (€)
- O&M (€ / year)
- Economic Saving (€ / year)
- Payback (years)

GENERAL RESULTS:		
Thermal self sufficiency:	7.10	%
Energy consumption saving:	17,205	kWh/year
Total demand:	420,042	kWh/year
Invest:	204,941	Euros
O&M:	4,099	Euros
Economic Saving:	20,490	Euros/year
Payback:	12.50	Years
CO2 emissions reduction:	131,372	kgCO2
Energy Cost:	15,584	Euros/year

Figure 4: Screenshot of the General Results interface. Source: CHESSE SETUP simulation software.

